

Gravitons as Dark Matter & Dark Energy

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Abstract

In keeping with the more informal aims of the Gravity Research Foundation, “short essays for *stimulating thought* and *encouraging work* on the phenomenon of gravitation”, we suggest that the long-standing and hitherto unsolved enigmas Dark Matter and Dark Energy can actually be explained and understood solely by gravity itself. More precisely in terms of gravitons, the expected quanta of the gravitational field. We briefly go through the arguments behind this conjecture, and some of its very interesting and far-reaching physical consequences.

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1 Introduction

Gravitons are the perfect Dark Matter. They are expected to exist, only interact gravitationally so are “invisible” to all other interactions, and are very poorly (if at all) constrained by present observational data. So, the “Dark Sector” may have been hiding in plain sight all the time. Despite decades of hard work, no signs of the many *exotic* Dark Matter candidates have been seen in experiments. The simplest explanation of this, in line with Occam’s razor, is that *exotic* Dark Matter *does not exist*.

A universe created by a quantum fluctuation [1], in a pure quantum state, would have had zero entropy and energy, *i.e.* $\Omega \equiv 1$, an exactly flat global universe. And as gravity, coupling nonlinearly to local energy-momentum, dominates all other interactions as $t \rightarrow 0$, *i.e.*, as $Q^2 \rightarrow \infty$, we can approximate the very earliest universe to contain only gravitons. As gravitons are not directly observable, we may assume that, at the big bang, $\Omega = \Omega_{gravitons} \equiv 1$. No empirical constraints presently forbid this, removing the need for (hypothetical) inflation, with all its *ad hoc* ingredients, to explain the observed flatness of the universe. And as gravitons created in the big bang are quantum (nonlocally entangled) it also removes the horizon problem.

The universe starts in a pure quantum state ($S \equiv 0$), but for each realization of an outcome (“measurement” \rightarrow event) the entropy increases by $S = -kTr(\hat{\rho} \log \hat{\rho})$, where $\hat{\rho}$ is the density matrix operator $\hat{\rho}_{nm} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N a_m^{(i)*} a_n^{(i)}$, and a_k quantum probability amplitudes.

If we approximate the universe by “nested” semi-local FRW-regions, the bound (matter) regions have $\Omega_{bound} > 1$ *increasing* in time due to gravity, while unbound (void) regions have $\Omega_{void} < 1$ *decreasing* in time as the universe expands ($\Omega_{void} \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$).

The present universe contains a weakly interacting “gas” of *physical* (not virtual) gravitons, which due to their gravitational interaction congregate where there is matter, and since gravitons themselves gravitate thereby enhance gravity in those regions, mimicking Dark Matter.

Natural fluctuations for gravitational systems are much *larger* than the usual \sqrt{N} valid

for *non*-gravitational systems. Also, a uniform density is *not* a gravitational equilibrium state. So, the standard *global* FRW-*model* of cosmology is obviously oversimplified as it (via the “cosmological principle”) assumes perfect, and eternal, spatial homogeneity and isotropy - something not observed in the *real* universe. The largest known structure is ~ 3000 Mpc [2], comparable to the size of the observable universe and clearly in conflict with the cosmological principle of FRW. Still, it is almost universally used, the main reason being that these unphysical assumptions reduce Einstein’s equations from an intractable set of ten coupled, highly nonlinear partial differential equations to an analytically solvable set of just two coupled ordinary differential equations (Friedmann’s equations), resulting in only one dynamical degree of freedom in the FRW-*model*, the uniform cosmic scalefactor $a(t)$.

However, as gravitons gravitate, the real “lumpy” universe get “runaway solutions” where gravity amplifies the effect of matter, the most extreme example being the formation of a black hole which in the end continues to exist solely due to this gravitational nonlinearity. In less extreme cases we still get important, cumulative, corrections to the naive (usually linearized) approximations normally employed, as cosmological observations are quite sensitive to the actual large-scale properties of the universe. As it long has been known that the universe has huge spongy structures - cosmic “filaments” and “voids” [3], the former containing all observable matter, whereas the latter seem essentially empty of such - these play a crucial but neglected role for both the dynamics and observations of the *real* universe, ever more so as structure formation proceeds, Fig. 1. The universe, according to *classical* general relativity, is an unchanging 4D-spacetime “block” of all invariant events. The global scalar curvature invariant (proportional to the Einstein-Hilbert action, and related to the Yamabe invariant of differential geometry) is

$$\int_{tot} R\sqrt{|g|} d^4x = A, \tag{1}$$

where $R = R^\mu_\mu = g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\nu}$ is the local scalar curvature, and g the determinant of the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of large-scale spatial structure, with gravitationally bound regions of overdensity (graviton concentration increasing in time) surrounding gravitationally unbound expanding regions of underdensity (graviton concentration ever decreasing). Just like soap in the bubbles of a bubble-bath is distributed to minimize nonlinear energy, observed voids and filaments analogously evolve.

For our classically causal (observable) universe since the big bang the spacetime 4-volume is finite. As its evolving 3D spatial hypersurfaces are non-simply connected, with evolving filamentary regions of overdensity, surrounding bubbly voids of underdensity, Fig. 1, for the regions of structure (observationally known to be almost “fractal-like”/scale-invariant and hierarchical), we have

$$\int_b R\sqrt{|g|} d^4x = B, \quad (2)$$

and for the gravitationally unbound void regions, using (1),

$$\int_u R\sqrt{|g|} d^4x = U = A - B. \quad (3)$$

From Einstein’s equations

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}, \quad (4)$$

where $T_{\mu\nu}$ locally encodes all non-gravitational energy-momentum, the scalar curvature al-

ways fulfills

$$R^\mu{}_\mu - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}R = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T^\mu{}_\mu, \quad (5)$$

i. e.

$$R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T. \quad (6)$$

And as we never have perfect vacuum in the real universe, only in idealized models, the scalar curvature is generally non-zero, and positive definite. So far the treatment has been formally exact and invariant.

Now approximating, for a perfect fluid in comoving coordinates in *homogeneous* and *isotropic* FRW-space

$$T = \rho(t)c^2 - 3p(t). \quad (7)$$

Hence, for an eternally expanding *global* FRW-universe T , and thus R , tends to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$. For pure radiation $p = \rho c^2/3$, giving $R_{rad} = 0$, so radiation does not contribute to the scalar curvature. The present matter-dominated FRW-epoch has $p \simeq 0$ (“dust”) and $R_{matter} = 8\pi G\rho(t)/c^2$. If a cosmological constant, Λ , corresponding to a constant *Dark Energy* is introduced in (4) via a term $\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$,

$$R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T - 4\Lambda, \quad (8)$$

then $R \rightarrow -4\Lambda = \text{const.}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, making (1) and the Einstein-Hilbert action ill-defined as the 4-volume goes to infinity; another, mathematical, reason to avoid Dark Energy quite apart from the physical reasons.¹

As a quantum treatment is necessary when the action over a characteristic 4-volume is less than or $\sim \hbar$, we see that a universe containing pure radiation (as in the earliest epochs, and the latest ones if the universe expands forever and black holes evaporate) really must be treated quantum gravitationally; only in intermediate epochs does the classical treatment

¹Two vastly different Λ 's at inflation and now, $\sim 10^{120}$ discrepancy between the theoretically expected value of Λ and the observationally inferred one, no known physical fields can generate Λ , etc.

apply. This also allows the possibility of small (quantum) inhomogeneities/fluctuations in the early universe, whereas the classical treatment is smooth - precluding “seeds” from which gravitational structures later could grow. We thus see that gravitons are a necessity for cosmology, not a luxury.

Dynamics, *i.e.* evolution, requires a 3+1-split of spacetime, destroying the globally invariant character of the 4D-spacetime “block”. However, cosmological structure formation introduces a physical “arrow of time” all by itself - the big bang model being isotropic in its spatial part only, not in time. Nevertheless, to obtain the observed large-scale structure in a “mere” 14 billion years, the standard FRW-model must be “doped” with *huge* amounts of Dark Matter (Λ CDM-model), much larger than the contribution from “normal” matter, as newtonian gravity used in N -body simulations of supposedly “small” perturbations in the assumed globally valid background FRW-geometry does *not* generate additional gravity. In full nonlinear gravity the “doping” is automatically provided by gravitation itself - as gravity *does* generate additional gravity [4] it will nonlinearly amplify the gravitation of matter present in bound regions.

2 Gravitons as Dark Matter

As gravitons are free as $Q^2 \rightarrow 0$, while gluons as $Q^2 \rightarrow \infty$ (asymptotic freedom/running of couplings), weakly interacting gravitons can exist as free physical particles whereas gluons never can [5]. Gravitons behave like “inversed” gluons: Strong and highly nonlinear as $Q^2 \rightarrow \infty$ (big bang), weak and perturbatively nonlinear as $Q^2 \rightarrow 0$ (today). Also, one high-energy graviton can convert into large numbers of low energy gravitons, not possible for matter particles carrying conserved quantum numbers. “Normal” statistical fluctuations $O(\sqrt{N})$ are not sufficient to explain structure in an expanding universe - but gravity supports and prefers much larger fluctuations, as its nonlinear interactions both “seed” and enhance structure formation. And just as the masses of protons, neutrons, and all other hadrons,

are completely dominated by gluons, not quarks, the masses of galaxies, clusters, and other gravitationally bound structures should be dominated by gravitons.

2.1 Normal Matter Creation by Gravitons

It is known that the only other nonlinear fundamental interaction with massless force-carrier particles, QCD, supports “string-like” characteristics of the effective force ($\neq 1/r^2$) due to the self-interaction of gluons. The same occurs for gravitons, as they too couple nonlinearly to themselves. If we, for illustrative purposes, assume that the effect just scales with the intrinsic strength between two protons (hydrogen being the main component of the visible universe) $F_{QCD}/F_{gravity} \sim 10^{38}$, the present characteristic length-scale of Gravity-string corrections comes out as $\sim 10^8$ lightyears \sim size of cosmic filaments and voids.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of effect without (QED: left) and *with* (QCD: right) nonlinear self-interaction. Gravity behaves similar to QCD, as gravitons, like gluons, nonlinearly self-interact. Above a threshold distance the effective force becomes \sim constant, the potential rising as $\sim r$, until it is favorable to create matter, which simultaneously gives an effective cut-off of the interaction. Heuristically, one can thus immediately see why matter should lie along filaments, Fig. 1. This should apply also to full general relativity, as gravity itself gravitates, but can no longer be described by a single simple potential.

Because gravitons are bosons, and also their own antiparticles, there are no quantum numbers that must be conserved. As the universe expands, some convert to matter pairs, so nothing but gravitons is required as $t \rightarrow 0$: Gravity, as it self-couples, gets a correction to its “field-lines”, Fig. 2. This then create matter, like “hadronization” in QCD, when the flux-tube is stretched it becomes energetically favorable to create new matter particles non-adiabatically out of the field. The scale of hadronization in QCD is ~ 10 fm, and as the work needed to create proton-pairs roughly is $F_{QCD} \cdot l_{QCD} \simeq F_{gravity} \cdot l_{gravity} = 2m_p c^2$, in cosmology present gravitational matter creation should take place at a scale of roughly 10^8 lightyears. Gravity then gets an effective cut-off above this scale, just like QCD disappears outside nuclei (even though gluons, like gravitons, are massless), explaining why the universe should seem statistically homogeneous and isotropic at scales $\gg 10^8$ lightyears.

As general relativity is *non-locally* neither CP nor CPT invariant, the CPT-theorem being valid only for Lorentz-covariance [6], strict particle-antiparticle symmetry need not apply, meaning that CP can be broken, *even* if T-reversal symmetry is still obeyed. However, it is the T-symmetry that conserves energy (Noether), and this too is broken in general relativity as an invariant definition of conserved *gravitational energy* is nonexistent. (Physically, this T-breaking is evident in the real universe, as *e.g.* gravitational structure formation defines what is to be considered “forwards” in time.) So, CP is broken globally, which means that a gravitational asymmetry between matter and antimatter is allowed, as also is observed. The very notion of “particle” is directly linked to the Poincaré group of *special* relativistic field theory. Its absence in the case of the gravitational field opens up for gravitational particle production (observed in asymptotically flat regions) by a time-varying $g_{\mu\nu}$: The generally covariant four-divergence $T_{;\nu}^{\mu\nu} = 0$ is not a conservation law but describes the *transfer* of energy and momentum [7] between (nonlocal) gravitation and (local) matter which is not conserved in the presence of dynamic spacetime curvature but changing in response to it. It is also an *empirical* fact that the weaker the interaction, the fewer conservation laws does it obey. So this aspect of gravity, presently by far the weakest of all known interactions,

is not entirely surprising. “Gravitation conserves everything or nothing depending on how you look at it” [8]. (As the invariant interval between the created quark-pairs in Fig. 2 is spacelike they don’t annihilate even if QCD conserves CP.)

Concretely, this dissipative effect enhances distribution of matter along the field lines, *i.e.* between the (initially tiny) anisotropic matter concentrations, making them ever more pronounced, explaining why matter is observed to increasingly concentrate along filamentary “string-like” structures.

3 Gravitons as Dark Energy

Measurements in the late 1990s on type Ia supernovae [9], [10] surprisingly seemed to indicate that the universe accelerates its expansion, instead of the deceleration unanimously expected if gravity is universally attractive. This eventually resulted in a “neo-standard” interpretation (Λ CDM), which is just FRW with a lot of “exotic” (completely unknown) ingredients, whereby the present universe is inferred to be dominated by some exotic Dark Energy $\Omega_{DE} \simeq 0.7$, whereas $\Omega_{matter} \simeq 0.3$ out of which almost all must be invisible *Dark* Matter $\Omega_{DM} \simeq 0.25$.

However, when taking the *real*, inhomogeneous and anisotropic matter distribution into account, there is no need for this, despite the data. As seen in the introduction, local curvatures must be integrated over all spacetime to obtain the global curvature of the universe, which seems compatible with zero from cosmic microwave background data. As gravitational structure formation relentlessly creates bound regions of increasingly positive curvature, the regions in between become ever more negatively curved in order to comply with a vanishing global curvature, meaning that the graviton density decreases there.

As structure formation proceeds and the universe expands, the cosmic “voids” increasingly contribute the bulk of the physical volume², this negative curvature, being an increasing

²As a non-expanding two-dimensional analogy, a flat sheet of metal if punched with small, sharp indentations “compensates” by curving the other way in between.

function of time, cosmologically mimics the effect of a mysterious, but fictitious, Dark Energy. This self-enhancing effect means that as gravitons increasingly concentrate along the matter filaments they decrease in the voids, making the voids relatively speed up. We empirically know that the “lumpiness” of the universe has monotonously increased with time. It then becomes natural that we should observe an (apparent) “acceleration” only in an epoch with appreciable void/filament structure formation. In the much simplified FRW standard model of cosmology with non-zero cosmological constant Λ , on the other hand, it is just a strange and completely unexplainable mystery why the “cosmic coincidence” $\Omega_{matter} \sim \Omega_{\Lambda}$ should occur *now*, as $\Omega_{matter} \gg \Omega_{\Lambda}$ as $t \rightarrow 0$, and $\Omega_{matter} \ll \Omega_{\Lambda}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Also, the very dynamics of the universe is altered due to these self-induced inhomogeneities, more prominently so as structure formation progresses. To make this important point more intuitively clear, the picturesque 2D “inflating balloon”-analogy for the universe can still be used, but with one crucial modification: The usual “coins” (representing gravitationally bound galaxies/galaxy clusters) glued to the surface must be replaced by “rubber bands” crisscrossing the balloon surface. Regions “in between” (voids) will then expand increasingly fast relative to the “rubber bands” (filaments of the cosmic web), giving an apparent acceleration between gravitationally *unbound* expanding “voids” and the complex gravitationally *bound* “filamentary” structure. Furthermore, in the *real* universe the “rubber bands” grow stronger, and the “voids” weaker (the balloon surface ever more pliable) as structure formation proceeds, making the effect ever more pronounced with time. As a result, it is automatically only after sufficient structure (“rubber band”) formation has taken place that a deviation from FRW and an “acceleration” should be observable, which means that *now*, when erroneously interpreted through the globally homogeneous and isotropic Λ CDM FRW-model, we would deduce (incorrectly) that “ $\Omega_{\Lambda} \sim \Omega_{matter}$ ”.

If we observe an inhomogeneous universe but “pretend” it is homogeneous, it will yield a correction for the inhomogeneity that behaves much like a cosmological constant [11]. This removes the need for mysterious Dark Energy - which is great as it has no fundamental,

microscopic explanation or justification whatsoever. The dynamics of a non-homogeneous universe without Λ mimics “acceleration” when interpreted through a (falsely assumed) homogeneous model [12]. The natural, more complex, variation of expansion rate with position in the real universe is then (falsely) interpreted as an additional variation in time, due to the finite speed (c) of information transfer.

4 Conclusions

Let’s be blunt: There is presently *no* direct evidence *whatsoever* of either exotic Dark Matter or Dark Energy. Despite *decades* of direct searches not *one* exotic Dark Matter candidate has been seen in experiments, while Dark Energy is not even viable to test on Earth. As Einstein’s equations are nonlinear, solutions do not superpose, unlike gravitational potentials in the newtonian approximation. The gravitational field of two galaxies is *not* the sum of the “individual” fields, let alone the huge number used in N -body simulations. But large N -body simulations have so far used only newtonian gravitation, linear in the gravitational potentials, which fail to reproduce the observed power-law behavior of large-scale structure in the real universe [13]. So, structure formation in the universe can be just another example of spontaneous self-organization, known to require nonequilibrium and nonlinearity [14]. A future theory of full, non-perturbative quantum gravity probably will neither respect time-reversal invariance nor CP-invariance, fundamentally explaining why there exist no free antimatter in the universe.³ The nonlinear aspects of gravity have so far been gravely underestimated in cosmology, but can perturbatively be treated via gravitons - which also impersonate Dark Matter and Dark Energy.

³Indeed, CPT-invariance is valid only for special relativity, *i.e.* only *locally* in free-falling reference-frames. As shown in section 2.1 even classical general relativity globally breaks CPT, CP and T.

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